

Studies on Reimer-Tiemann Reaction.

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A systematic investigation of the Reimer-Tiemann reaction described in this communication, wherein the influence of the nature and position of substituents has been studied, has revealed that when chloroform (or carbon tetrachloride) is mixed with alcohol (1:3) the yield of the aldehyde (or the acid) is increased. It has also been found that in some cases where the sodium salt of the phenol is sparingly soluble *e.g.*, in the cases of *o*-bromophenol and 2-hydroxy-anthraquinone, the addition of a little pyridine to the alkali solution greatly helps the reaction, but however, the nitrophenols are not helped to an appreciable extent by this. It is interesting to note that aqueous pyridine may entirely replace alkali hydroxide solution; from phenol, salicylaldehyde being formed in this way in a yield of 10 per cent. whilst *p*-hydroxybenzaldehyde is not produced at all.

When Reimer-Tiemann's reaction is applied to *o*-coumaric acid, the entrant aldehyde-group attacks the *para* position only. Similar results are obtained also with 8-hydroxyquinoline where the *para* derivative is formed (30 per cent.) to a greater extent than the *ortho* (16 per cent.). *o*-Nitro- and bromophenols are converted into the corresponding aldehydes much better than the *para* analogues. Similarly *o*-bromophenol gives a better yield of the acid than the *para* compound with carbon tetrachloride.

The influence of negative substituents (NO_2 , Cl, Br and SO_3H) on the reaction is to inhibit the reaction as is to be expected, the nitro group exerting the maximum effect. This may also be partly due to the very sparing solubility of the alkali salts of nitrophenols and also to the specific inhibiting action of the nitro group, because negative groups like COOH (*cf.* aldehydosalicylic acid, yield 27 per cent., Wayne and Cohen, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1922, 121, 1022), SO_3H (*cf.* aldehydophenol sulphonic acid, yield 21 per cent., *vide infra*) alone do not suppress the reaction to a very great extent.

The reaction has been successfully applied to thiophenol (yield 3.5 per cent., thioalicylic acid with carbon tetrachloride), 2-hydroxy-

anthraquinone (yield 25 per cent. of the *ortho*-aldehyde), 8-hydroxyquinoline (yield 16 per cent. of *ortho* and 30 per cent. *para* aldehydes) and to thymol which gives 17 per cent. of *ortho*- and 11 per cent. of *para*-aldehydes.

The new aldehydes described in this paper condense to give interesting dyes which will be described subsequently.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Salicylaldehyde and p-hydroxybenzaldehyde.—When a mixture of phenol (50 g.), chloroform (50 c.c.) and alcohol (150 c.c.) was stirred into a solution of sodium hydroxide (100 g. in 160 c.c. water) at 60° for 4 hours, gave 18 g. of salicylaldehyde and 3.5 g. of *p*-hydroxybenzaldehyde, after working up in the usual way.

A mixture of chloroform (15 c.c.) and alcohol (45 c.c.) and a solution of phenol (15 g.) in aqueous pyridine (50 g. in 30 c.c. water) when heated at 100° for 30 hours gave 2 g. of salicylaldehyde.

Salicylic acid and p-hydroxybenzoic acid.—By heating phenol (50 g.) carbon tetrachloride (85 g.), alcohol (200 c.c.) and caustic soda solution (110 g. in 176 g. water) for 36 hours, 7.3 g. of salicylic acid and 2 g. of *p*-hydroxybenzoic acid were formed. The yield was only 5 p.c. without using alcohol.

3-Nitrosalicylaldehyde.—A solution of nitrophenol (50 g.), chloroform (36 c.c.) and alcohol (120 c.c.) was added drop by drop to caustic soda solution (62 g. in 100 c.c. water) and heated on a water-bath for 8 hours. The brownish mass separated on acidification with hydrochloric acid, was washed with water and finally crystallised from alcohol, m.p. 109°, yield 5.4 g. It was found identical with the compound prepared by nitration of salicylaldehyde (Miller, *Ber.*, 1887, 20, 1928). (Found: N, 8.42. $C_7H_5O_4N$ requires N, 8.38 per cent.). It forms a monoacetyl derivative (m.p. 150°) identical with the acetyl derivative of 3-nitrosalicylaldehyde of Miller (*loc. cit.*).

2-Nitro-4-hydroxybenzaldehyde was prepared from 3-nitrophenol exactly as in the previous case. The aldehyde was separated by dissolving in hot benzene, in which it is more soluble than 3-nitrophenol. It was finally crystallised from water, m.p. 67°, yield 1.2 g. from 50 g. of *m*-nitrophenol. It was found identical with the aldehyde and its phenylhydrazone (m.p. 189°) prepared by Sachs and Kantorowicz (*Ber.*, 1906, 39, 2754).

5-Nitrosalicylaldehyde was prepared from *p*-nitrophenol, and purified through the bisulphite compound, the yield being 3 g. from 30 g. of *p*-nitrophenol. It was found identical with the aldehyde prepared by Miller (*loc. cit.*).

3-Bromosalicylaldehyde and *3-bromo-p-hydroxybenzaldehyde* were prepared from *o*-bromophenol (25 g.) chloroform (15 c.c.), alcohol (50 c.c.) and sodium hydroxide solution (27.5 g. in 50 c.c. water). The temperature was kept at 50-60° initially for 3 hours and the mixture was then heated on the boiling water-bath for 6 hours. The thick red oil, separating on acidification, was distilled in steam and the *o*-aldehyde crystallised from dilute alcohol in pale yellow crystals, m.p. 52°, identical with the aldehyde prepared by Müller (*Ber.*, 1909, 42, 695) by reduction of *3*-nitrosalicylaldehyde and then by diazo-reaction. Yield 3.8 g. The aldehyde forms a semicarbazone (m.p. 266°) identical with the semicarbazone of the aldehyde prepared by Müller.

The mother-liquor from which the *o*-compound had been removed, was treated several times with boiling water to extract the *p*-aldehyde. The aqueous extract on cooling, deposited colourless crystals of *3*-bromo-*p*-hydroxybenzaldehyde, which was further crystallised from chloroform, m.p. 124°, yield 1 g. It was found identical with the aldehyde prepared by bromination of salicylaldehyde (Hantzsch and Mai, *Ber.*, 1895, 28, 2469).

The *semicarbazone* crystallised from alcohol in almost colourless needles, m.p. 195-96°. (Found: N, 16.45. $C_8H_5O_2N_3Br$ requires N, 16.28 per cent.).

If in the above reaction pyridine (15 c.c.) be added to the alkali, the yields of the *o*- and *p*-aldehydes increase to 5 g. and 1.5 g. respectively.

5-Bromosalicylaldehyde was prepared from *5*-bromophenol and purified through the bisulphite compound, m.p. 104°, yield 2.5 g. It was found identical with the compound prepared by bromination of salicylaldehyde (Henry, *Ber.*, 1869, 2, 275; *ibid.*, 1889, 22, 1135; Auwers and Walker, *ibid.*, 1898, 31, 3042; Auwers and Burger, *ibid.*, 1904, 37, 3934).

The *semicarbazone* crystallised from alcohol in colourless needles decomposing at 297°. (Found: N, 16.6. $C_8H_5O_2N_3Br$ requires N, 16.3 per cent.).

3-Bromo- and 5-bromosalicylic acids were prepared from *o*- and *p*-bromophenols respectively. A mixture of *o*-bromophenol

(2.5 g.), carbon tetrachloride (17 c.c.), alcohol (50 c.c.) and caustic soda solution (36.5 g. in 73 g. water) was heated for 12 hours on the water-bath. The acids were isolated from their barium salts by acidification.

3-Bromosalicylic acid was found identical with the compound prepared from 3-bromo-5-aminosalicylic acid (Lellmann and Grothmann, *Ber.*, 1884, 17, 2715); it crystallises from 50 per cent. methyl alcohol, m.p. 184°, yield 0.5 g. The barium salt crystallises in red prisms from hot water (*cf.* Meldrum and Shah, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1923, 123, 1986). [Found: Ba, 21.68; H₂O, 9.12. (C₇H₄O₃Br)₂Ba, 3H₂O requires Ba, 21.99; H₂O, 8.66 per cent.].

5-Bromosalicylic acid crystallises from boiling water, m.p. 164-65°, yield 0.3 g. It was found identical with the compound prepared by the action of phosphorus tribromide on salicylic acid (Henry, *loc. cit.*; Hand, *Annalen*, 1886, 234, 133; 1893, 273, 122). (Found: Br, 36.97. C₇H₅O₃Br requires Br, 36.8 per cent.).

5-Chlorosalicylaldehyde was prepared from *p*-chlorophenol as in the preparation of 3-bromosalicylaldehyde. It was purified through the bisulphite derivative and found identical with the compound prepared from salicylaldehyde (Biltz and Stept, *Ber.*, 1904, 37, 4024; Piria, *Annalen*, 1851, 80, 196), m.p. 99.5°, yield 0.9 g. from 25 g. phenol. The semicarbazone melts at 286-87° and was found identical with the semicarbazone of the aldehyde prepared by Biltz and Stept. (*loc. cit.*).

5-Chlorosalicylic acid, identical with the compound prepared by Beilstein (*Ber.*, 1875, 8, 816) was prepared from *p*-chlorophenol (25 g.) carbon tetrachloride (200 c.c.) and caustic soda solution (45 g. in 90 c.c. water). The acid crystallises from hot water, m.p. 167.5°, yield 0.2 g.

1-Aldehydo-2-hydroxybenzene-3-sulphonic acid was prepared from phenol-*o*-sulphonic acid (10 g.) chloroform (10 c.c.), alcohol (35 c.c.) and caustic soda solution (20 g. in 32 c.c. water). The aldehyde crystallises from hot water in golden yellow needles. It is soluble in hot water, sparingly soluble in alcohol, insoluble in ether, chloroform acetone and benzene; it does not melt below 250°. (Found: S, 16.00. C₇H₆O₅ S requires, S, 15.84 per cent.).

*5-Aldehydo-*o*-coumaric acid*, CHO·C₆H₃·OH (CH:CH·COOH) (5:2:1).—A solution of *o*-coumaric acid (15 g.) and chloroform (14.5 g.) in alcohol (30 c.c.) was added to a solution of caustic soda (23 g. in 80 c.c. water) as in the preparation of 3-bromosalicylalde-

hyde, but the heating was continued for 12 hours. The brick-red powder, separated on acidification, was filtered hot. The aldehyde separated from the filter on cooling, and was crystallised from dilute alcohol in pale yellow microcrystalline needles, m.p. 220° (decomp.), yield 1.8 g. It is described identical with the aldehyde by Sen and Chakravarti (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1930, 7, 249). (Found: C, 62.41; H, 4.20. $C_{10}H_8O_4$ requires C, 62.50; H, 4.16 per cent.).

The *silver salt* was prepared in the usual way as yellow powder. (Found: Ag, 36.3. $C_{10}H_7O_4Ag$ requires Ag, 36.1 per cent.).

The *phenylhydrazone*, prepared in the usual way, crystallised from dilute acetic acid as a yellow microcrystalline powder, m.p. 236° (decomp.). (Found: N, 10.22. $C_{16}H_{14}O_3N$ requires N, 9.92 per cent.).

The *semicarbazone* prepared in the usual way, crystallised from dilute alcohol in almost colourless microcrystalline powder, m.p. 275°. (Found: N, 16.7. $C_{11}H_{11}O_4N_3$ requires N, 16.86 per cent.).

6-Aldehydocoumarin.—5-Aldehydo-*o*-coumaric acid (2 g.) was dissolved in the least quantity of concentrated sulphuric acid and heated on the water-bath for 2 hours. When poured into water, it deposited a brown mass, which was filtered, treated with sodium carbonate solution to remove the unchanged 5-aldehydo-*o*-coumaric acid. It crystallised from alcohol, m.p. 187-89°. It was found identical with the aldehyde prepared by Stoermer and Oetker (*Ber.*, 1904, 37, 192) and Sen and Chakravarti (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1928, 50, 2428).

*5-Carboxyl-*o*-coumaric acid*, $COOH \cdot C_6H_3 \cdot OH$ ($CH:CH \cdot COOH$) (5:2:1).—*o*-Coumaric acid (15 g.) and carbon tetrachloride (17 g.) dissolved in alcohol (35 c.c.) was added drop by drop to caustic soda solution (26.5 g. in 42.5 g. water) and the solution heated on the water-bath for 20 hours with vigorous stirring. The separation of the dicarboxylic acid was effected as in the case of 5-aldehydo-*o*-coumaric acid. It crystallised from alcohol in pale yellow needles, decomposing at 186° and finally melting at 210°, yield 0.5 g. It is soluble in hot water, hot alcohol, and acetone; sparingly soluble in cold alcohol; insoluble in ether, chloroform and benzene. It gives reddish colour with ferric chloride.

Di-silver salt was prepared in the usual way from ammonium salt as yellow powder. (Found: Ag, 51.23. $C_{10}H_6O_5Ag_2$ requires Ag, 51.18 per cent.).

2-Methyl-5-isopropyl-6-hydroxybenzaldehyde.—A solution of thymol (15 g.) and chloroform (16 g.) in alcohol (90 c.c.) was added drop

by drop to caustic soda solution (20.5 g. in 38 c.c. water) and the whole heated on the water-bath to 30° to start the reaction. The stirring was continued for 5 hours at the room temperature. The deep red oil, separating on acidification, was submitted to distillation with steam when the *o*-compound separated as a pale yellow oil. This was taken up with ether and purified through the bisulphite compound, b. p. 233°, yield 3 g. It is insoluble in water and soluble in alcohol, ether, chloroform and petroleum ether; gives an intense violet coloration with ferric chloride. (Found: C, 74.00; H, 8.01. $C_{11}H_{14}O_2$ requires C, 74.15; H, 7.86 per cent.).

The *semicarbazone*, prepared in the usual way crystallised from alcohol as colourless tiny needles, m.p. 242°. (Found: N, 18.10. $C_{12}H_{17}O_2N_3$ requires N, 17.86 per cent.).

6-Methyl-3-isopropyl-4-hydroxybenzaldehyde.—After the removal of *o*-aldehyde with steam, the non-volatile *p*-compound remained as a brownish-red substance. The aqueous portion was filtered hot, the residue dissolved in caustic soda and precipitated by neutralising with acetic acid. The process was repeated four or five times. The aldehyde was crystallised from dilute alcohol in brownish needles, m.p. 108-10°, yield 2 g. It is insoluble in water and petroleum ether; easily soluble in alcohol, ether and chloroform; it gives no coloration with ferric chloride. (Found: C, 73.77; H, 8.21. $C_{11}H_{14}O_2$ requires C, 74.15; H, 7.85 per cent.).

The *semicarbazone* crystallised from alcohol as pale yellow needles, m.p. 191°. (Found: N, 18.03. $C_{12}H_{17}O_2N_3$ requires N, 17.86 per cent.).

7-Aldehyde-8-hydroxyquinoline.—A mixture of 8-hydroxyquinoline (15 g.), chloroform (14 g.), alcohol (60 c.c.) and sodium hydroxide solution (16.5 g. in 28 c.c. water) was heated at 100° for 12 hours. Alcohol and the excess of chloroform were driven off. The solution was made just acidic with hydrochloric acid when a brick-red powder separated which was washed first with ether to remove the unchanged hydroxyquinoline and then with chloroform. The chloroform solution furnished the 7-aldehyde-8-hydroxyquinoline which crystallised from a mixture of chloroform and alcohol in reddish microcrystalline powder melting above 250°, yield 3 g. It is insoluble in water, alcohol, acetone, carbon tetrachloride and benzene; easily soluble in chloroform, pyridine, quinoline, and acetic acid; it gives a greenish yellow coloration with ferric chloride. (Found: N, 8.15. $C_{10}H_7O_2N$ requires N, 8.09 per cent.).

5-Aldehyde-8-hydroxyquinoline.—The residue left after removal of the *ortho*-compound with chloroform crystallised from boiling quinoline as brownish powder, melting above 250° , yield 5.5 g. It is insoluble in water, ether, chloroform, carbon tetrachloride, acetone, benzene and alcohol; soluble with difficulty in nitrobenzene and quinoline; easily soluble in acetic acid and pyridine; gives no coloration with ferric chloride. (Found: N, 8.22. $C_{10}H_7O_2N$ requires N, 8.09 per cent.).

1-Aldehyde-2-hydroxyanthraquinone.—A solution of 2-hydroxyanthraquinone (10 g.) and chloroform (10 c.c.) in alcohol (60 c.c.) was added to caustic soda solution (10 g. in 16 c.c. water) and heated on the water-bath for 30 hours. The olive-brown mass, separating on acidification, was washed with hot water and dried; the unchanged 2-hydroxyanthraquinone was removed with boiling nitrobenzene; the aldehyde was washed with petroleum ether. It can be crystallised from a very large excess of boiling nitrobenzene as yellowish powder melting above 300° , yield 1.8 g. It is insoluble in all ordinary organic solvents; soluble with difficulty in boiling carbon disulphide and boiling nitrobenzene; easily soluble in pyridine. (Found: C, 71.23; H, 3.17. $C_{15}H_8O_4$ requires C, 71.42; H, 3.17 per cent.).

Thiosalicylic acid.—A solution of carbon tetrachloride (11 c.c.) in alcohol (30 c.c.) was added to a mixture of thio-phenol (14 g.) and sodium hydroxide solution (23 g. in 33 c.c. water) and the mixture heated for 30 hours on the water-bath. On acidification, a little pale yellow mass separated out; the unchanged thio-phenol was distilled off with steam; the solid residue filtered, washed with water and crystallised from alcohol, m.p. 163° , yield 0.5 g. It was found identical with the compound prepared from *o*-chlorobenzoate and potassium hydrosulphide (D.R.P. 189200). (Found: S, 20.92. $C_7H_6O_2S$ requires S, 20.77 per cent.).

